

HOUSEHOLD SIZE AS CORRELATE OF POVERTY AND CHILD VULNERABILITY IN THE NORTH-WEST GEOPOLITICAL ZONE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The research focuses on socio-cultural and socio-economic variables to basically ascertain whether household size could correlate with poverty and child vulnerability in the North-West, Nigeria. Two research objectives were raised to guide the study. They sought to determine whether household size is significantly related to poverty in the North-West and also whether household size was related to child vulnerability in the North-West. Two hypotheses were formulated in a null form tested at 0.05 level of significance. The first hypothesis stated that there was no significant relationship between household size and poverty in the study area. The second stated that there was no significant relationship between household size and child vulnerability in the study area. Correlational design was adopted in the study. Using multi-staged cluster, 278 sampled households were used in the study. The findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between household size and poverty $r = .768, p = .00 < .05$. Also, there was a significant relationship between household size and child vulnerability $r = .771, p = .00 < .05$. It was recommended among others that the tradition of maintaining household size should be reviewed. This could be by way of accepting religious sermon, use of contraceptives, and public enlightenment campaigns to clear misconceptions.

Keywords: Household, Vulnerability, Poverty

Introduction

Nigeria strives harder to achieve certain National Developmental Goals which include enhancing security, achieving high quality infrastructure, improving educational outcome, enhancing trade and transport among others. However, for a country to be in tune with these developmental needs, there must be some pre-requisites such as socio-political, socio-cultural and socio-economic stability. Nigeria is yet to achieve meaningful development in spite of her huge resource endowment which affected quest to having improved quality of life of her citizens. Consequently, poverty, unemployment, starvation, inequality, illiteracy and child vulnerabilities still pervade in the country.

In Northern part of the country, the security threats are mostly in the North-east and the North-west regions with the North-west being currently the most volatile region. The North – west is one of the six Geo – political divides in Nigeria, comprising seven states which are Kano, Kaduna, Katsina, Jigawa, Kebbi, Sokoto and Zamfara. It is a native homeland of

Hausa people with the second largest tribe being Fulani. According to the Humanitarian Needs Overview Nigeria, (2022), the North-west has a population of over 40 million people. It occupies a land mass of up to 193,088 km². It is in recent times being plagued by incessant attacks of banditry. According to the International crisis group, (ICG) (2020), the zone suffers deadly conflict involving many armed organizations. About a hundred groups of bandits with over 30,000 militants operate in the region. They terrorize herders' settlements, farms, villages and high ways with the missions of killing, maiming, raping, cattle rustling and kidnapping accompanied by merciless demand of ransom among others. Most of those affected by the banditry are local farmers and as a result, food production shrinks. Amnesty international reports, (2020) posit that 33,130 people, mostly farmers have been displaced in rural farming communities of North-western Nigeria.

Furthermore, abductions of school children have become the region's new normal. In December 2021, passengers were ambushed and burnt to death in Sokoto state. The state government says 21 passengers including children died of injuries sustained from the burns. (Guardian, December 8, 2021). Recently, another attack was executed on 28th March, 2022, in which an Abuja – Kaduna boarded train was involved in Katari, Kaduna state, Nigeria. BBC news of 27th April, 2022, reports that at least 9 passengers died during the attack and some 168 were reportedly missing afterward. Between October, 2013 to March 2014 about 7,000 cattle were rustled in the zone. Also, between January and July, 2019, 330 attacks were mounted leading to the death of 1,460 people.

The North-western region of Nigeria faces a situation of high fertility and low contraceptive use. This is driven in large part by high-fertility norm alongside cultural and religious beliefs, misconceptions about contraceptives among others. Nigeria accounts for more than 1 in every 5 out of school children in the world. In spite of being free and compulsory, 39% of children that should be in school in the North-west (with the exception of Kaduna) are not in classes. Also, analysing poverty rate by gender by political zones put North-west as the highest with 77.7% whereas the South-west as the least with 49.8% (Jaiyeola & Bayat, 2019). Nigeria has a high rate of illiteracy of up to 60 million or 30% of its entire population. According Federal Ministry Education (FME) the national literacy rate in Nigeria is 65.1%. Female literacy rate in the North-west is only 38.0% meaning 62% stands out to be illiterate. Male literacy rate in the North-west was 57.5%.

Judging from above, it is being speculated in most documented researches that banditry is caused by religion and or politics. This research focuses on other socio-cultural and socio-economic variables not focused by the previous researchers. The motivation behind this research work is to basically ascertain the extents to which household size relates with poverty and child vulnerability in the North-West.

Purpose of the Study

This research project specifically seeks to determine:

1. Whether household size is significantly related to poverty in the North-West geopolitical zone, Nigeria.
2. Whether household size is significantly related to child vulnerability in the North-West geopolitical zone, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

With a population of over 40 million people, the North-West geopolitical zone of Nigeria is the most populated zone in the country and also one of the largest in terms of landmass. It is a Muslim, Hausa-Fulani dominated zone, consequent upon which religion and cultural practices have made family patterns and structure polygamous in nature. The major occupations of the people are farming practices and nomadic herding. Recently the zone is under siege as numerous attacks are being wedged on school pupils leaving severe impact on education, on farmers leaving food insecurity, and travellers

thereby affecting markets, trades and distribution of goods and services. Consequently, the North-west has traditional large household sizes and there are indices of high poverty rate and child vulnerabilities which necessitate the conduct of the study.

Literature Review

Household is defined as a group of persons who make common provision of food, shelter and other essentials for living as a fundamental socio-economic unit in human societies. Households are the centres of demographic, social and economic processes. Decisions about childbearing, education, health care, consumption, labour force participation, migration and savings occur primarily at the household level. Understanding the trends and patterns of household size and composition can thus inform efforts towards the achievement of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (United Nations Database on Household Size and Composition, 2017).

Globally, average household size ranges from three persons per household to more than six persons. In 2019 average household size in sub-Saharan Africa was reported to be 6.9 people per household, comparatively, the smallest average household size was Europe with 3.1 people per household (Szmigiera, 2021). It is important to note that, household characteristics such as size and composition are closely related with sustainable development, poverty and well-being in general (United Nations Department of Economics, Social and Political Affairs Division, 2017).

In Nigeria, according to the National Statistical Office, number of households reached 43.0 million in 2020. This is 2.52% more than in the previous year. Historically, this is an all-time high. The average household size in Nigeria is 5.0 person. It is slightly higher in the rural areas than in urban areas [5.1 versus 4.7 persons]. The top five states with highest household sizes are Bauchi, Jigawa, Niger, Kano, and Katsina.

Household Socio-Economic Characteristics

Household's Literacy: In 2012, UNESCO gave an outline of literacy rate in Nigeria with Lagos, Osun and Anambra states having literacy percentages of 92.0, 80.0 and 75.1 respectively. During the same year in question, Kebbi, Jigawa, Taraba, Katsina and Borno states were reported to have percentage literacy rates of 25.3, 24.2, 23.3, 21.7 and 14.5 respectively. It is worth noting that three of the least states are from the North-west Geopolitical zone of Nigeria. Recently, 76 million Nigerian adults were reported to be illiterates by the Federal Government (Tribune, September 7, 2021).

Household's Occupation: Nigeria's unemployment rate in 2020 by states according to Statista, (2022) international methodology outcomes put Zamfara as having 41.70%, Kaduna 22.65%, Jigawa 41.29%, Kano 31.20%, Katsina 23.54%, Sokoto 19.18%. These indices have direct linkages with earnings and standard of living which are not unrelated to hardships and child vulnerability.

Household's Income: Every four out of ten Nigerians live below the poverty line. Just 17% of Nigerian workers hold the wage jobs best able to lift people out of poverty (World Bank, 2022). They further submit that sluggish growth, low human capital, labour market weaknesses and exposure to shocks are holding Nigeria's poverty reduction back. Of the estimated population of 206 million people, 91 million Nigerians fall below poverty line (Vanguard, January 2022). This figure is expected to reach 95 million in 2022 (World Bank, 2022). Autograph as cited in Muhammad, 2017 using Nation Bureau for statistics data on poverty ranking in the six Geopolitical zones in Nigeria has put the North-west as the highest level with 71.4%.

Child Vulnerability

Child vulnerability in Nigeria and other low and middle-income countries around the world is an important development challenge that needs a multi-sectoral intervention approach (UNICEF, 2017). This is because the plight of vulnerable children poses a significant challenge to achieving goals 1-5 of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). To address challenges related to poverty, hunger, education, good health, and gender equality, development partners need to work with relevant stakeholders in both rural and urban communities in Nigeria (Nnama-Okechukwu, Agwu & Okoye, 2020). Given the increasing number of children categorized as vulnerable and in need of care and protection, there is a need to prioritize resources and develop social intervention programmes to address causative factors (Bamgboye et al., 2017)

A review of the available literature shows that several socio-cultural factors are responsible for child vulnerability in Nigeria. For instance, a study showed that the major cause of child vulnerability in Nigeria is poverty (Abdullahi, 2020). Some studies further linked causes of vulnerability to harmful cultural and religious practices like child marriage, Osu-caste system, child witchcraft, female genital mutilation, and Almajiri institution (Anyacho & Anyacho, 2016). Recently, increasing social problems such as Boko Haram insurgency, inter-communal crisis, herdsmen attack, and occasional natural disaster such as flooding leading to internal displacement are contributing factors promoting child vulnerability in Nigeria (Gwadabe, Salleh, Ahmad & Jamai, 2018).

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted correlational research design since it was aimed at determine relationships between variables. According to Kowakzyk (2015) in a correlational design, a measure of a relationship is sought between two variables.

Sampling

The totality of all households in the seven states of the North-west geopolitical zone, Nigeria, constitutes the population of interest to this project. Since it is difficult to access all the households in the seven states, their sub-set (sample) would be selected for this project. Because of the nature, size and distribution of the population of interest to this project, the researchers adopt multi-stage cluster sampling technique. In multi-stage cluster sampling, a researchers chose a sample in two or more stages because either the researchers cannot easily identify the population or the population is extremely large and difficult to obtain their list (Creswell, 2012).

North-west geopolitical zone of Nigeria has seven states which might be thought of as having seven clusters. The researchers randomly selected four Local Governments Areas (LGAs) ($7 \times 4 = 28$). From 28 local governments areas, the sample of the subjects (households) to be used in the study were obtained. The next stage will be to select at random from each of these 28 LGAs four wards. Finally, 5 households might be selected at random from each ward. By implication, 28 LGAs multiplied by 4 wards give 112 sample points (wards) which when multiplied by 5 household heads will give a total of 560 sample size to be used in this study. This is supported by Cochran's sample size determination formula, (1977) which records that if there were just 1,000 households in the target population, 278 households are adequate and substantial.

Method of Data Collection

The instrument for data collection used in this study was a structured questionnaire which was designed on Likert 5-point scale.

Method of Data Analysis

The objectives of this study are to relate variables therefore, correlational statistical tests are to be used to determine the degree of relationship between and among variables. This project therefore, adopts correlational design. In correlational designs, investigators use the correlational statistical test to describe and measure the degree of association or relationship between two or more variables (Creswell, 2012). In order to analyse the data for this project, Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used.

Result

Table 1: Correlation between household size and poverty in the North-west geopolitical zone, Nigeria.

Correlated Variables	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value	Decision
Household size	3.10	0.977	0.768	0.00	Significant
Poverty	3.95	1.146			

The result of the analysis in the above table shows that using PPMC the coefficient of $r (3.10/3.96) = .768, p = .00$. This indicate strong positive correlation which mean as household sizes increase, the poverty level tends to be higher indicating that the relationship between household size and poverty is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis there is no significant relationship between the two variable is rejected.

Table 2: Correlation between household size and poverty in the North-west geopolitical zone, Nigeria.

Correlated Variables	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value	Decision
Household size	3.95	1.105	0.771	0.00	Significant
Child Vulnerability	3.05	1.033			

The result of the analysis in table 2 above shows that PPMC was calculated and the coefficient of relationship obtained is $r (3.95/3.05) = .771, p = .00$. The coefficient of r indicated strong positive correlation which means as household size increases, child vulnerability also tends to increase. From this analysis it could be deduced that the relationship between household size and child vulnerability is statistically significant.

Summary of findings

1. There is statistically significant relationship between household size and poverty $r = .768, p = .00 < .05$
2. There is statistically significant relationship between household size and child vulnerability $r = .771, p = .00 < .05$

Recommendation

Based on the finding of the study

1. The tradition of maintaining of household sizes should be reviewed. This could be accepting religious sermon, use of contraceptives and public enlightenment campaigns to clear misconceptions.
2. Poverty and child vulnerability require multi-sectoral intervention approach. The two put together pose significant challenges to security and achievement of sustainable development goals.

Conclusion

Given that household size significantly relates with poverty and child vulnerabilities, more seriousness should be put on seeing that challenges relate to hunger, illiteracy, good health, unemployment and also studied un relation to household sizes that are culturally expanding beyond measure.

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